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Experimental investigation of fuel conversion characteristics during co-combustion of solid recovered fuel and coal in a 1 MW_{th} circulating fluidized bed reactor

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ABSTRACT

This study presents experimental results on co-combustion of hard coal and solid recovered fuel (SRF) conducted in a circulating fluidized bed (CFB) reactor with an internal diameter of 0.59 m, a height of 8.6 m, and a thermal load of 1 MW_{th}. The high flexibility of the test facility enables testing of a variety of input materials under changing test conditions. The combustion of various fuel mixes ranging from 100 % hard coal to 100 % waste was tested to assess the impact of varying fuel ratios on the overall combustion process. As the proportion of SRF increased, a reduction in reactor differential pressure and particle density was observed. Moreover, combustion shifts to higher parts in the reactor when the share of SRF is increased. To further investigate the combustion conditions inside the reactor, three in-bed gas measurements were conducted, capturing the horizontal gas profiles of CO₂, O₂, and CO. An increase in SRF content led to elevated CO and O₂ levels, alongside a reduction in CO₂, indicating an upward shift in the combustion zone. The behavior is attributed to the higher volatile content of SRF, which is in this experiment roughly 2.5 times the share of volatiles in hard coal and the lower bulk density of SRF. The study concludes by proposing potential strategies for reducing the impact of high SRF content on combustion conditions.

1. Introduction

Mitigating climate change requires the reduction of greenhouse gases in a variety of sectors. With a global share of roughly 38 % of CO₂ emissions worldwide in 2022 [1], the energy sector plays a crucial role in achieving the goals for reaching net-zero greenhouse gas emissions [2,3]. One option for a significant reduction of CO₂ emissions from existing coal-fired fluidized bed power plants is the transition towards fuels with a lower carbon footprint, such as biomass and waste.

Biomass has a lower carbon footprint compared to coal and can potentially remove CO₂ from the atmosphere, when combined with a carbon capture and storage (CCS) process [4]. Although biomass is a very broad term and local differences must be taken into account, the values of the volatile components and fixed carbon in e.g. the studies by Chiang et al. [5], where mainly biomass of Asian origin was examined, and by Dieringer et al. [6], where biomass of European origin was used,

are in similar ranges with values of 60 to 80 percent by weight for the volatile components and up to 20 percent of fixed carbon. The proximate analysis of the feedstocks used in this study reveals that biomass has a similarly high volatile content as SRF, but significantly lower fixed carbon compared to coal. This suggests that biomass could also be a promising feedstock for the use in CFB power plants. However, when considering biomass as a fuel for CFB combustion systems, it is important to recognize its limited availability and the competition between biomass cultivation for energy and food production for a growing global population. In the future, it is likely that residual biomass will be considered too valuable for combustion and instead be used as a carbon source in thermochemical conversion processes for producing basic chemicals and for closing the carbon cycle [7].

The global production of waste, on the other hand, will continue to increase in the future, growing from 1999 megatons (Mt) in 2015 to 3539 Mt in 2050 [8]. In 2018, 70 % of global waste was sent to landfills

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[9], and landfilling is expected to remain a significant disposal method in the future [8]. By sorting and thermally utilizing the non-recyclable fraction of waste, it is possible to replace coal, which currently account for up to 100 % of the fuel in some fluidized bed power plants. This leads to a reduction in CO₂ emissions from power plant and landfill operations and furthermore protects the environment, as less areas have to be created for landfill. Additionally, operators of existing fluidized bed power plants can extend operations beyond coal phase-out dates, enhancing their economic viability. Industry and the private sector also benefit from this transition, as it ensures continued energy security through reliable electricity and heat generation, complementing renewable sources such as solar and wind.

The substitution of coal by waste in existing CFB power plants presents numerous challenges. Hydrodynamic and thermodynamic conditions within the riser are critical for the long-term operation of these facilities. Additionally, changes in fuel composition, particularly the increased chlorine content, pose significant challenges for system components such as the heat exchanger surfaces or the refractory lining. Kim et al. investigated the co-combustion of 5 % SRF in a commercial boiler fired with anthracite, maintaining stable temperatures and pressures while observing elevated HCl emissions [10]. Soleh et al. studied a 25 MW commercial CFB power plant using low rank coal, replacing 5 % of the fuel feed with SRF pellets, noting a slight temperature rise in the upper part of the boiler and observing agglomerate build-up in the bed material [11]. Peters et al. demonstrated operational stability during co-firing of up to 28 % SRF with low-rank coal [12]. Qin et al. tested four

different fuel mixtures, ranging from 0 to 30 % waste co-combustion with coal gangue [13]. Contrary to Soleh et al., they observed an increase in bed temperature with higher SRF percentages.

While some studies have tested varying proportions of SRF, they commonly involve only adding a small amount of SRF to coal. Additionally, the focus of other coal and SRF co-combustion research has been on examining flue gas composition [14,15] or corrosion phenomena [16]. Oxyfuel combustion is also frequently discussed in conjunction with co-combustion, particularly when biomass is used as a coal substitute [17–21].

As none of the previous studies systematically replaced coal by waste up to 100 % while analyzing the hydrodynamic and thermodynamic behavior of the boiler, tests were conducted in a 1 MW_{th} semi-industrial pilot plant with the following objectives:

- Examination of the impact of varying fuel compositions, including up to 100 % SRF, on the thermodynamic and hydrodynamic behavior of the reactor.
- Evaluation of the gas composition across the full width of the reactor at a height of 4.2 m above the nozzle grid for different fuel mixtures.
- Application of the findings from pilot tests to commercial combustion systems.

Fig. 1. Experimental setup of the 1 MW_{th} pilot plant.

2. Experimental

2.1. Layout of 1 MW_{th} pilot plant

The experimental setup of the 1 MW_{th} pilot plant is shown in Fig. 1. The reactor has an inner diameter of 0.59 m and a total height of 8.6 m. It is fully refractory lined according to industrial standard to minimize heat losses. In general, two types of fuel, namely hard coal and SRF were fed to the CFB via separate feeding systems. A screw conveyor was used to transport the coal in a controlled manner from the storage container to the rotary valve above the loop seal. In contrast, the SRF material flow from a second storage container to the same rotary valve was controlled via a belt conveyor. From there, both fuels enter the reactor directly via the rotary valve and the return leg between the loop seal and the reactor. This setup allows the variation of the mass flows of the two fuels independently of one another and thus different fuel mixtures can be tested. The electrically preheated combustion air is introduced to the CFB600 via the nozzle grid and partly via secondary air inlet nozzles at different heights (2.74 m and 6.00 m). The separation of particles and flue gas is realized via a cyclone, and particles return to the reactor via the loop seal. After heat removal in the heat exchanger, the flue gas stream can be directed through the pilot flue gas cleaning system (CFBS) for further treatment or directly to the environment via the bag filter. Three different ports can be used for analyzing the composition of the flue gas. The first port is located between the cyclone and the heat exchanger, where a paramagnetic sensor (O₂) and nondispersive infrared (NDIR) sensors (CO, CO₂, NO and SO₂) are used. Two more measuring ports are located before the CFBS and behind the dust filter, using Fourier-transform-infrared-spectroscopy (FTIR) (CO₂, CO, H₂O, SO₂, HCl, NO_x, CH₄). The temperature inside the reactor can be controlled with a total of five cooling lances, which can be inserted from the reactor top in two bundles of two lances each and a single one. The temperature and pressure are measured continuously over the entire reactor height. Additional description of the pilot plant can be found in the work of Alobaid et al. [22] and Peters et al. [12,23,24].

2.2. In-bed gas measurement setup

The in-bed gas measurements are conducted by means of an uncooled sampling lance (see Fig. 2), which is mounted in the sidewall of the reactor at a height of 4.2 m above the nozzle grid. A stuffing box seals the flue gas in the reactor from the environment while allowing axial movement of the lance to enable the recording of radial concentration profiles in the reactor.

The lance shown in Fig. 2 contains an integrated pre-filter, which separates the larger particles of the bed material from the sampled gas. Between the sampling lance and the gas analyzers, a finer main filter provides additional protection against contamination with fine fly ash. Both filters can be flushed with pressurized air to keep the flow

Fig. 2. Flow scheme of the gas sampling equipment.

resistance low during all measurements. All components shown in red are insulated and electrically heated to 200 °C to prevent condensation of moisture within the filters, valves, and hoses. To begin recording the concentration profiles, the lance is inserted into the reactor at a defined insertion depth. The gas analyzer pulls flue gas from the reactor for approximately 5 min, where after purging and cleaning, repositioning steps are conducted in preparation for the next insertion depths. The described procedure is repeated until the gas composition through the entire width of the reactor has been recorded.

Fig. 3 shows a scheme of a section through the reactor. It is important to note, that although the port for the in-bed gas measurement, the ports for the secondary air injection and the fuel supply are not at the same reactor height, they are illustrated in Fig. 3 in order to better clarify their position relative to one another. The port of the in-bed gas measurement (4.2 m above the nozzle grid) can be seen on the left side. The two entrances to the lower level of the secondary air (2.74 m above the nozzle grid) are arranged at an angle of approximately 35° clockwise and 145° counterclockwise. The fuel supply (0.48 m above the nozzle grid) occurs at an angle of 135° counterclockwise from the direction of the in-bed gas measurement.

2.3. Materials

Quartz sand was used for initial buildup of reactor inventory. The

Fig. 3. Reactor scheme with ports for in-bed gas measurement, fuel feed and secondary air.

sand was additionally fed to the system during the course of the test campaign to maintain a constant reactor inventory while simultaneously being able to remove metal residues, which are introduced into the reactor via the SRF. For the fresh material, a bulk density of 1375 kg/m^3 and a mean particle size of $199 \mu\text{m}$ ($d_{p,10} = 138 \mu\text{m}$, $d_{p,90} = 291 \mu\text{m}$) was determined. The feedstock used for pilot testing was a bituminous coal from Poland (see Fig. 4) and a commercially available SRF (see Fig. 5), provided by the German company Meinhardt Stadtreinigung GmbH & Co. KG, which consisted mostly of plastic, paper, textile, wood and foams.

The specific data for both fuels listed in Table 1 show that both feedstocks have clear differences in the proximate analysis. The proportion of fixed carbon and volatiles is particularly important for thermodynamic investigations, as both influence the location of the thermal conversion inside the reactor. The difference in ash content is of high interest regarding the hydrodynamic investigation. The mercury measurement of the SRF was carried out according to DIN EN ISO 12846 (2012–08), where atomic absorption spectrometry (AAS) was employed. No such data is available for coal.

2.4. Operating conditions

As part of a 10-day test campaign in March 2023, during which the 1 MW_{th} pilot plant was continuously operated 24 h/day, co-combustion tests of coal and SRF were performed in a total runtime of 156 h. After more than 24 h of 100 % coal firing, the share of SRF was increased stepwise. After each change in the fuel mixture, the boundary conditions were kept constant until stable thermodynamic and hydrodynamic conditions were established in the reactor. Once firing of 100 % SRF was reached, the fuel feed was kept constant for more than 36 h to investigate long term effects of the combustion of waste on operational stability. During the entire period, the thermal input was kept in a range from 600 to 900 kW_{th} , with average values around 725 kW_{th} . As outlined in Chapter 2.3, metal and glass residues are introduced into the reactor via the SRF and must be removed to ensure continuous plant operation. To manage this, material is periodically extracted from the bottom of the reactor in a time-controlled process. To compensate for the resulting pressure drop, fresh quartz sand is simultaneously fed to the system via the rotary valve (see Fig. 1) to maintain constant pressure in the bed area. This method ensures discharge and feeding rates even up throughout the test campaign.

Fig. 4. Bituminous coal used during pilot testing.

Fig. 5. SRF used during pilot testing.

Table 1
Fuel characteristics for SRF and polish coal.

	Description	SRF	Coal
Proximate analysis	Moisture [wt-% a.r.]	22.00	11.80
	Ash [wt-%, dry]	6.60	20.40
	Volatiles [wt-%, dry]	85.15	30.80
	Fixed Carbon [wt-%, dry] (calculated: 100 % – Rest)	8.25	48.80
Ultimate analysis	C [wt-%, dry]	61.67	64.52
	H [wt-%, dry]	8.51	4.19
	N [wt-%, dry]	1.01	1.13
	O [wt-%, dry]	21.09	8.98
	S [wt-%, dry]	0.14	0.61
	Cl [wt-%, dry]	0.98	0.18
DIN EN ISO 12846 (2012–08)	Hg [mg/kg]	< 0.1	n.a.
LHV (lower heating value)	[MJ/kg, a.r.]	20.86	21.91
Mean particle size (D50)	[mm]	–	5.15
Maximum particle size	[mm]	10.0	10.0
Bulk density	[kg/m ³]	96	704

3. Results and Discussion

Table 2 shows a selection of six different test periods with the most important parameters for each period. All periods have been selected for further investigation of temperature and pressure profiles in the reactor, while the periods II, IV and V have additionally been selected for analysis of in-bed gas measurements. The primary air for test period I through IV has been electrically heated to 60 °C, while it has been heated to 150 °C for test periods V and VI to counteract the higher moisture content of SRF. The secondary air has been electrically heated to 80 °C for all test periods, as higher temperatures were not possible in the secondary air pipes due to technical limitations.

3.1. Operating regimes of selected test periods

The first step in comparing the selected test periods against each other is the classification of the operating regimes of the particles in the fluidized bed. The diagram similar to Fig. 6 was first introduced by Kunii and Levenspiel [25], where they referenced the work of Grace [26] to be able to predict the behavior of gas–solid mixtures in fluidized beds. The

Table 2
Selected test periods from co-combustion tests.

Operation point	Load [kW _{th}]	Load share [%]		Primary air share [%]	Secondary air share [%]	Superficial Velocity [m/s]	Duration [h]
		SRF	Coal				
I: pure coal	668	0	100	65	35	4.2	3.5
II: pure coal	636	0	100	65	35	4.1	2.25
III: fuel mixture tests	655	57	43	58	42	3.8	3.7
IV: fuel mixture tests	821	74	26	56	44	4.0	1.9
V: pure SRF	762	100	0	53	47	4.0	4.4
VI: pure SRF	727	100	0	52	48	4.1	4.0

Fig. 6. Grace diagram indicating the operational regimes for the selected test periods [25].

dimensionless particle diameter d_p^* , plotted on the x-axis, is calculated according to equation (I), where the particle diameter of the bed material d_p , the density of the gas ρ_g and the solid particles $\rho_{s,g}$, the gravity force g and dynamic viscosity μ are implemented to calculate the Arrhenius number according to equation (II).

$$d_p^* = Ar^{1/3} \quad (I)$$

$$Ar = \frac{d_p^3 \rho_g (\rho_{s,g} - \rho_s) g}{\mu^2} \quad (II)$$

The dimensionless superficial velocity u_0^* (see equation (III)), which is plotted on the y-axis, is calculated using the particle Reynolds number and the dimensionless particle diameter d_p^* . The particle Reynolds number is calculated with the particle diameter of the bed material d_p , the mean velocity inside the reactor u_0 , the density of the gas ρ_g and dynamic viscosity μ (see equation (IV)).

$$u_0^* = \frac{Re_p}{d_p^*} \quad (III)$$

$$Re_p = \frac{d_p u_0 \rho_g}{\mu} \quad (IV)$$

The marks for all test periods listed in Table 2 are located very close to each other in the circulating bed regime. This indicates that similar hydrodynamic conditions exist within the reactor, enabling a

comparison of the temperature and pressure profiles across each test period.

3.2. Temperature and pressure profiles

The pressure in the pilot plant is measured as absolute pressure against the surrounding and is influenced by the induced draft (ID) fan. A comparison of pressure profiles can therefore only be made when the relative pressure for each test period is considered. For this purpose, the pressure difference at each measurement point was calculated relative to the measurement taken at the reactor exit at a height of 8.0 m above the nozzle grid for each test period.

The pressure difference profiles along the reactor height for each of the six test periods can be seen in Fig. 7. It is important to note that the reactor height of 0 m is referenced directly above the nozzle grid and the maximum height of the reactor is 8.6 m. The test periods show typical pressure profiles for CFB combustion, implying high differential pressure in the lower part of the reactor (height of 0–1 m) followed by lower differential pressures in the upper part of the reactor. As the differential pressure is in direct correlation with the amount of material inside the reactor, a high particle density can be concluded in the lower part, which is also called bed zone, and a low particle density in the upper area, the so-called free board zone. Comparing the cases of 100 % coal combustion and 100 % SRF combustion, the differential pressure for coal combustion is generally higher over the entire height of the reactor. Due to the direct correlation between the differential pressure and the amount of particles in the reactor, overall higher amounts of particles in

Fig. 7. Differential pressure profile over reactor height.

the reactor can be concluded for the combustion of 100 % coal. This finding can be explained with the approximately three times higher share of ash in coal compared to SRF (see Table 1), contributing to the formation of circulation material, which results in increasing solids density. The pressure profile of the combustion of mixtures of coal and SRF are as expected between the other pressure profiles over the entire reactor height. This finding supports the thesis of a slight decrease of bed pressure when the SRF share is increased.

Table 3 presents the thermal input, insertion depth, and the inlet and outlet temperatures of the cooling water for the three cooling lances used during the test periods, along with the combined thermal output of the cooling lances across all six test periods. A comprehensive description of the cooling system, including details on the five different cooling lances can be found in the work of Peters et al. [12,23,24]. The cooling performance of each individual lance could not be calculated, as only the total volumetric flow of the cooling system was recorded.

The comparison of the first two test periods, in which 100 % coal was burned, shows that the total cooling output in test period 2 decreases by 4.6 %, which can be explained by a reduction in thermal load of 4.8 %. In test period three, the fuel composition changes (see Table 2) along with the thermal load, while cooling lance three is simultaneously inserted further into the reactor. This results in a disproportionate increase of the thermal output of the cooling lances of nearly 20 %, compared to a 3 % rise in thermal load. The impact of the position change of lance 3 is evident in the cooling water outlet temperature, which rises by 19 K, in contrast to the outlet temperatures of the other two lances, which decrease by 2 and 3 K. The increase in thermal load during test period 4 does not lead, contrary to expectations, to a further rise in the cooling performance of the lances. In the subsequent periods 5 and 6, where 100 % SRF is burned, both the thermal input load and the cooling performance of the lances decrease. Due to the heterogeneous composition of the RDF and the associated difficulty in calculating the fuel supply, the constant cooling performance of the lances suggests that the thermal load in test periods 5 and 6 might be overestimated. This issue often arises for operators of commercial facilities, which is why control is frequently based on measurable plant parameters rather than on the calculated fuel mass flow.

Another aspect that should be considered is that a significant portion of heat transfer to the cooling lances occurs via conduction. Therefore, it can be assumed that the previously described decrease in bed material with the increase in the SRF fuel fraction negatively impacts the heat transfer to the cooling lances. However, since this is just one of many factors, its impact cannot be quantified definitively.

Fig. 8 and Fig. 9 show the temperature and the temperature difference profiles along the reactor height for the six test periods. It is important to point out that although the reactor is only 8.6 m high, the top measuring point is given at 9 m. The temperature at 9 m height refers to a measurement of the exhaust gas temperature after the cyclone, which is important for the quantification of combustion taking place inside the cyclone. The positioning of the cooling lances, which are inserted from the top of the reactor to control temperature regulation, is presented alongside the profiles for each test period. Notably, the positions of cooling lances 1 and 2 remained constant throughout all test periods, while cooling lance 3 was inserted deeper into the reactor

Fig. 8. Temperature profile over reactor height.

before test period III.

Although there are differences in the absolute temperatures of the six test periods presented in Fig. 8, the general trend is similar. This implies high temperatures in the bed region (0–1 m), followed by a temperature decrease in the free board zone, which is induced by the cooling lances. The combustion is sub stoichiometric below the secondary air addition due to the secondary air share of 35 to 48 % (see Table 2). The temperature increase between the measuring height of 5.24 m and 6.26 m can therefore be explained by the addition of secondary air at a height of 6 m above the nozzle grid, which adds additional oxygen to the reactor. This results in increased oxidation and thus more heat release and a rise in temperature. The difference in absolute temperatures between the cases of 100 % coal combustion and the other test periods is due to the fact that one cooling lance was inserted deeper into the reactor after examining the test points of 100 % coal combustion (I and II in Table 2), as well as a change in thermal input (see Table 2). Although secondary air I is added at a height of 2.45 m above the nozzle grid, there is no noticeable increase in temperature. This can be explained by the cooling lances being inserted from the reactor top to a height of 2.6 m above the nozzle grid and the cooling capacity locally being greater than the heat release of the combustion induced by the secondary air I.

Table 3

Selected parameters for evaluation of cooling lances.

Test period	Thermal load [kW _{th}]	Insertion depth [m]		Cooling water inlet temperature [°C]	Cooling water outlet Temperature [°C]			Thermal output [kW]
		L1 + L2	L3		L1	L2	L3	
I: pure coal	668	6	2.25	110	138	140	120	196
II: pure coal	636	6	2.25	110	136	138	119	187
III: fuel mixture tests	655	6	5.7	110	133	136	138	224
IV: fuel mixture tests	821	6	5.7	110	133	135	137	221
V: pure SRF	762	6	5.7	110	130	132	134	190
VI: pure SRF	727	6	5.7	110	130	132	134	190

Fig. 9. Temperature difference profile over reactor height.

In order to compensate for the effect of the different thermal loads (see Table 2), as well as the varying number of cooling lances inserted into the reactor and thereby to be able to compare the relative temperature profiles of the test periods, the temperature difference profiles are shown in Fig. 9. For this purpose, the temperature difference at each measurement point was calculated relative to the lowest measurement taken at a height of 0.245 m above the nozzle grid for each test period.

The temperature difference profiles in Fig. 9 show only small deviations up to the fifth measuring position at a height of 6.26 m. The temperature of each test period decreases in the subsequent range from 6.23 m to the highest measurement inside the reactor at 8.23 m, but begin to deviate more from each other. A general trend can be observed of temperatures decreasing less sharply as the proportion of SRF in the fuel increases.

When comparing the measurements 6 and 7 at the reactor height of 8.23 m and behind the cyclone respectively, the connection between the fuel composition and the change in temperatures is clearly visible. While drops of 49 and 43 K can be seen in the two test periods when 100 % coal is combusted, this effect slows down as the SRF share increases. When burning 57 % SRF and 43 % coal in test period III, a temperature reduction of only 3 K can be seen. The trend continues, so that with a SRF share of 74 %, an increase of 10 K can already be seen in the temperature behind the cyclone. During the subsequent investigation of 100 % SRF as feedstock, the temperatures between the reactor top and behind the cyclone increase by 70 and 75 K respectively. This finding can be explained by the fact that with increasing SRF content and thus increasing content of volatile components in the fuel, the combustion shifts to higher reactor areas. Similar results have been found by Soleh et al. [11] and Gulyurtlu et al. [27]. As soon as the residence time is no longer sufficient to fully mix the components, which would result in a complete oxidation until the reactor outlet, part of the oxidation takes place in the cyclone. A second aspect that leads to a shift of combustion to higher reactor areas is the low bulk density of SRF and its high share

of volatile components (see Table 1). Due to the fast release of the volatiles, combustible components are transported more quickly to higher reactor areas, while some of the volatile components are already oxidized on the way upwards. However, due to air staging and the local lambda being less than one below the addition of secondary air II, some of the oxidation takes place above this point.

3.3. Flue gas composition

Table 4 presents the thermal load, the volume flows of primary and secondary air, the total fluidization, the calculated superficial velocity, as well as the oxygen and carbon dioxide concentrations in the flue gas downstream of the cyclone. During the test operation, a superficial velocity of 4 m/s and a residual oxygen contents of 5 to 6 vol-% were targeted for the various fuel mixtures and loads. As expected, the residual oxygen content increases in the second test period with a simultaneous reduction of the thermal load and a constant overall fluidization. Due to the higher oxygen content in the SRF compared to coal (see Table 2), the residual oxygen content in test period three falls into the target range, although the total fluidization is decreased and the thermal load is increased. In the other test periods, the changed fuel mixture is still clearly visible, as the residual oxygen content is kept constant despite a disproportionate increase in the thermal load in relation to the increase in total fluidization. These results are in line with expectations and show no correlation with the results of the temperature profiles presented previously.

3.4. In-bed gas measurements

Three in-bed gas measurements were conducted during the co-combustion tests. The corresponding test periods in Table 2 are numbers II, IV and V. It should be reiterated that the in-bed gas measurements were conducted at a fixed reactor height of 4.2 m above the nozzle grid, allowing for the gas profile to be measured on a path of 0.59 m from one reactor side to the other. The measurements in the second and fourth test period were conducted in incremental horizontal steps of 50 mm between each measurement position, resulting in 12 measurement points. The measurement in test period V was conducted in smaller steps, resulting in a total of 28 measurement points. All gas components are measured on dry basis, while the moisture content is measured in the flue gas downstream of the ID-fan. The measurements across the entire width of the reactor cannot be carried out simultaneously, but take place one after the other. The x-Axis in Fig. 10 to Fig. 12 therefore represent not only a spatial but also a temporal separation of the measurements. In comparison to the other components, the moisture content only represents a temporal resolution due to its constant measuring position behind the ID-fan. Since the measurement position of the moisture content in the flue gas is not changed during the entire process and full oxidation can be assumed to have taken place behind the ID-fan, the moisture content is supposed to not fluctuate between the different measurement positions. However, due to the inhomogeneous composition of the fuel, and particularly due to fluctuations in moisture and hydrogen content, the moisture content in the exhaust gas can vary between the different measurement depths. Therefore, the moisture content in the exhaust gas can serve as an indicator of the fuel composition's homogeneity during the measurement period. In addition, by comparing the absolute values of the moisture content of the three measurements, a conclusion can be drawn about the connection between the fuel mixture of coal and SRF, and the development of the moisture content in the flue gas.

The mean values and error bars in the following figures are obtained by calculating the mean values and standard deviation of the measured values at each measurement depth.

Fig. 10 shows the gas profile of the in-bed measurement during the combustion of 100 % coal. The moisture content has an average value of 5.1 % with fluctuations between 3.8 and 5.8 %. The gas concentrations

Table 4
Selected parameters for evaluation of flue gas composition.

Test period	Thermal load [kW _{th}]	Primary air [Nm ³ /h]	Secondary air [Nm ³ /h]	Total fluidization [Nm ³ /h]	Superficial velocity [m/s]	Flue gas O ₂ [Vol-%, dry]	Flue gas CO ₂ [Vol-%, dry]
I: pure coal	668	567	300	867	4.2	5.8	13.2
II: pure coal	636	567	300	867	4.1	6.8	12.3
III: fuel mixture tests	655	486	351	837	3.8	5.3	13.0
IV: fuel mixture tests	821	486	381	867	4.0	5.3	12.1
V: pure SRF	762	465	417	882	4.0	5.3	11.7
VI: pure SRF	727	465	427	892	4.1	5.4	11.7

Fig. 10. In-bed gas measurement during the combustion of 100% coal.

are relatively constant throughout the reactor with low values for CO. A slight increase can be seen in O₂-values between the measurement depths of 300 to 500 mm. As the moisture content in the flue gas simultaneously decreases, a temporarily different composition of the fuel can be assumed. The uniformity of the gas composition of each species across the other areas of the reactor indicates homogeneous mixing and even combustion throughout the reactor.

Fig. 11 shows the gas profile of the in-bed measurement during the

Fig. 11. In-bed gas measurement during the combustion of 74% SRF and 26% coal.

Fig. 12. In-bed gas measurement during the combustion of 100% SRF.

combustion of 74 % SRF and 26 % coal by heating value. The moisture content has an average value of 7.9 % with fluctuations between 7.4 and 8.1 %. The fluctuations decreased, compared to the first measurement, which is an indication for more stable fuel composition. The increase in absolute moisture content can be explained by the substitution of 74 % of the coal feed by heating value with SRF and its higher moisture content and share of hydrogen (see Table 1), which are both roughly twice the share compared to coal. Comparing Fig. 10 and Fig. 11, on average higher values for CO and O₂ can be noted in Fig. 11, while CO₂ values are lower. This finding can be attributed to the ~ 2.75 times higher share of volatiles in SRF with a simultaneous reduction of roughly 80 % of fixed carbon (see Table 1). The reduction of the combustion of fixed carbon with instead the increase of release of volatile components in the bed zone results in a combustion partly taking place further up in the reactor and even above the gas composition measurement height of 4.2 m above the nozzle grid, compared to pure coal combustion. The increase in CO and CO₂ values with the simultaneous decrease of O₂ values, starting at a measurement depth of 300 mm, is an indication for an unsymmetrical combustion taking place inside the reactor, which has not been observed to the same extent during the combustion of 100 % coal. This finding can be attributed to the fuel feeding taking place on the right-hand side of the reactor (compare Fig. 3), together with the very fast release of the volatile components of the SRF. The combustion of solid carbon, on the other hand, is much slower. In conjunction with the higher proportion of solid carbon in the coal, there are more char particles in the bed zone of the reactor when coal is burned. The longer time to complete oxidation of the char in combination with the higher proportion of char leads to better mixing of fuel and inert bed material, resulting in a more uniform gas profile when pure coal combustion is investigated – even in higher reactor zones (see Fig. 10). As a result of the increased share of SRF, a higher proportion of the fuel is partially or

completely oxidized directly upon supply before mixing occurs in the bed area, which creates the asymmetry of the gas composition across the width of the reactor.

Fig. 12 shows the gas profile of the in-bed gas measurement during the combustion of 100 % SRF. The moisture content has an average value of 8.9 % with fluctuations between 8.7 and 9.2 %. It is important to point out that moisture values could not be recorded when the in bed gas measurements were taken from 0 to 220 mm reactor depth due to technical problems. When comparing Fig. 12 with the previous one, a further increase in absolute moisture content can be observed with increasing share of SRF in the fuel composition. The above-mentioned trend of increased values for CO and decreased values of CO₂, which appear due to the increased share of SRF, can also be found in Fig. 12. In contrast to the other two measurements (Fig. 10 and Fig. 11), Fig. 12 shows a clear increase in the O₂ content in the center of the reactor. At the same time, the values for CO and CO₂ decrease in the center of the reactor. The decrease of O₂ content with a simultaneous increase in CO and CO₂ on both side walls of the reactor support the thesis of the core-annulus approach [25] taking place in the reactor with the particles and gases flowing upwards in the center of the reactor and the particle flows directed downwards at the reactor edge. This phenomenon was demonstrated by Daikeler et al. [28] for the pilot plant used to conduct the study. The downwards particle movement on the side walls of the reactor leads to a locally lower gas velocity and thus to longer residence times of the gases. Due to the longer residence time and higher contact time, there is a greater conversion of oxidizable components, leading to higher CO and CO₂ values along with lower O₂ values. Similar findings regarding CO and O₂ distribution have been made by Zhao et al. [29]. Similar to Fig. 11, Fig. 12 also shows an increase in CO and CO₂ values with a simultaneous decrease in O₂ values on the right hand side of the reactor, starting at a reactor depth of 300 mm. Since the absolute values of CO and CO₂ are higher and O₂ are lower than in the range of 0–100 mm reactor depth, it can be concluded, similar to the previous measurement, that the effect of the position of the fuel supply can be observed here. This effect's increase compared to the previous measurement confirms that the fuel change from coal to SRF is the underlying cause. Furthermore, it can be assumed that the previously mentioned effect—poorer mixing of char and bed material due to reduced char content and a more inhomogeneous gas composition—can also be observed when the SRF share of the fuel is increased to 100 %.

3.5. Transfer of pilot test results to commercial combustion applications

The pilot tests have shown that changing the fuel from coal to 100 % SRF leads to changes in hydrodynamics and thermodynamics. In particular, fuel switching results in less accumulation of bed material due to the lower ash content. In addition, the combustion shifts to higher reactor areas due to the increase in the volatile components of the fuel and the reduced proportion of fixed carbon. The rapid reaction kinetics of the release of the volatile components together with the reduction of the amount of char in the bed zone lead to inhomogeneous combustion within the reactor. Various measures, which could be taken to counteract these changes, are introduced in this section.

The decrease of bed pressure can be counteracted in different ways. The first option is to optimize the amount or interval of ash withdrawal from the system so that its residence time increases. When implementing this step, however, care must be taken to ensure that no agglomerates form due to the long residence time of the material in the reactor. The second factor that needs to be considered is the accumulation of coarse particles from the SRF. Despite careful pretreatment, SRF may contain ceramic or metal residues that must be removed from the process regularly to ensure good circulation. Therefore, in addition to increasing the residence time of the ash, it may be advisable to continuously add fresh bed material in the form of sand to the process or, if this is already being done, to increase the feeding rate. This would lead to an increase in the extraction rate, which would counteract the first measure. Due to

the regionally different composition and preparation of SRF, it is therefore difficult to conclude a general statement. Instead, the procedure should be adapted to local circumstances on a case-by-case basis.

Three options can be implemented to counteract the shift of combustion to higher reactor areas. The first option is the shift of fluidization medium from primary air towards secondary air. By locally reducing the fluidization velocity in the bed zone, the residence time of particles is increased which allows for more combustion taking place in the bed zone. One important aspect to consider when doing so is to keep the fluidization in the bed area high enough so that solid circulation is kept stable. A second option could be the implementation of a high velocity jet gas stream in the upper part of the reactor. This would lead to additional turbulences and horizontal mixing of gases inside the reactor, which would result in a more homogenous gas distribution. The gas stream does therefore not necessarily contain additional oxygen but could also be e.g. recirculated flue gas. A third option could be the change of bed material from sand towards ilmenite and implement so called oxygen carrier aided combustion (OCAC), which has been tested elsewhere providing promising results [30–32]. With its capability to absorb and release oxygen [33–35], ilmenite is capable of transporting oxygen from areas with high excess oxygen to areas of high demand, like the bed area near the fuel feed. As seen in this research, the lower proportion of fixed carbon of SRF compared to coal is a factor in the inhomogeneous distribution of the gas composition inside the reactor. To counteract this problem, other waste materials such as those from biomass gasification and pyrolysis or the paper industry, which have a higher proportion of fixed carbon, could be added in addition to SRF.

When structurally modifying the power plant, the possibility of splitting up and distributing the fuel supply into the reactor over several positions should be considered when changing to 100 % SRF, so that the asymmetrical combustion shown in these tests is avoided.

4. Conclusions

The experimental results of the pilot tests offer insight into the influence of varying fuel compositions on process characteristics such as the thermodynamics, the hydrodynamics, as well as the gas composition inside the reactor. These characteristics are of high interest regarding the substitution of coal with SRF in retrofitting commercial CFB power plants. The results of the pilot tests focusing on furnace conditions show the possibility of substituting coal with up to 100 % SRF. The substitution of high ash coal with SRF leads to a reduction of differential pressure over the entire reactor height and therefore towards lower amounts of circulating material. This effect can be counteracted with an optimization of the amount and interval of ash withdrawal, as well as the feed rate of fresh bed material. Increasing the share of SRF up to 100 % leads to a reduction of fixed carbon with the simultaneous increase of the volatile components in the fuel. The change in fuel compositions results in a shift of combustion to higher reactor areas, which can be seen by increased temperatures in the upper reactor area and in the flue gas temperature after the cyclone. In addition, an asymmetry of combustion can be seen in the reactor, if the fuel supply is not evenly distributed across the reactor. To counteract both effects, a shift from primary to secondary air can be implemented, a high velocity gas stream can be installed for additional mixing of the gas components, and the bed material can be changed so that it can bind and release oxygen locally.

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CRedit authorship contribution statement

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Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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Data availability

Data will be made available on request.

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